

Master Thesis of Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring Gender Distribution in Music Recommender Systems

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Abstract

Music Recommender Systems (mRS) are designed to give personalised and meaningful recommendations of items (i.e. songs, playlists or artists) to a user base, thereby reflecting and further complementing individual users' specific music preferences. Whilst accuracy metrics have been widely applied to evaluate recommendations in mRS literature, evaluating a user's item utility from other impact-oriented perspectives, including their potential for discrimination, is still a novel evaluation practice in the music domain. In this work, we centre our attention on a specific phenomenon for which we want to estimate if mRS may exacerbate its impact: *gender bias*. Our work presents an exploratory study, analyzing the extent to which commonly deployed state of the art Collaborative Filtering (CF) algorithms may act to further increase or decrease artist gender bias. To assess group biases introduced by CF, we deploy a recently proposed metric of *bias disparity* on two listening event datasets: the LFM-1b dataset, and the earlier constructed Celma's dataset. Our work traces the causes of disparity to variations in input gender distributions and user-item preferences, highlighting the effect such configurations can have on user's gender bias after recommendation generation.

Keywords: Music Recommender Systems; Gender Bias; Impact-oriented Evaluation;

Chapter 1

Introduction

Possibility is not a luxury; it is as crucial as bread.

- *Judith Butler, Undoing Gender* [1]

In recent years, several publications [2, 3, 4] have shed light upon the issue of unfair gender treatment in Recommender Systems (RS), raising questions of accountability, group-fairness and foremost, how to quantify and mitigate such unfair treatment of item and user groups. As the complexities of state of the art RS and their filtering methodologies deployed grow, *algorithmic-transparency* becomes an across party cause for concern whereby the logic underlying filtering methodologies must be reverse engineered to mitigate disproportionate treatment. Prior to the latter, it is first imperative to experimentally explore user and item configurations which may result in the distortion of user gender preference and more globally, the amalgamation of social values embedded. We centre the attention of this work on the former, tracing the bi-directional impact of gender in music recommender systems (mRS) at an offline level and ultimately, assessing the extent to which commonly deployed filtering algorithms can diminish or propogate a gender bias.

1.1 Motivation

Our work will contribute towards further understanding the influence of gender embedded in the *informational landscapes* of mRS, shedding light on the potential undesired outcomes which may be found to arise through varying *user-item* configurations. Whilst in academia, issues of disproportionate user/item treatment in RS has been extensively considered by the likes of organisations such as ACM FAccT ¹, FAT/ML ² and AIES ³, only a minimal amount of research of this nature has been carried out in the Music Information Retrieval domain (MIR) exploring the impact of gender in mRS.

Such literature gaps are contrary to the growing interdisciplinary critique of a disproportionate gender treatment being present in the music domain. Historically, since the modern music industry instantiation, female artists have been underrepresented in the popular music industry [5], with recent reports showing no sign of this trend easing ⁴. The motivation of this work is to address such inter-disciplinary concerns in the music domain, filling the void of MIR literature focusing on the intersection of gender and mRS. At a higher level, this work also aims to contribute towards achieving shared European ethical values of trust as recently outlined in the European Commission’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI ⁵. Specifically, the scope of this work will focus on contributing towards three of these values closely tied to the notion of gender equality - *diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*.

¹<https://facctconference.org/>

²<https://www.fatml.org/>

³<https://www.aies-conference.com/2020/>

⁴<http://assets.uscannenber.org/docs/aai-inclusion-recording-studio-2019.pdf>

⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

1.2 Objectives

Figure 1: Evaluation framework of the user experience for recommender systems, according to [6]

The objective of this work is not to reverse engineer filtering algorithms commonly deployed in mRS but rather instead, assess the impact of gender at one temporal stage of influence. Indeed, as detailed in Figure 1, objective system aspects (OSA) and user characteristics, attitudes and behaviours are outlined as fundamental components to be considered in a state of the art RS evaluation framework, capturing the impact of an RS at both a system and user-centric level.

Ultimately, this work considers Objective System Aspects of an mRS (OSA), studying the degree to which user preference for an artist gender can be distorted in generated recommendation lists. We devise an exploratory study, testing memory, model and baseline approaches for one of the most commonly deployed filtering algorithm taxonomies in mRS: Collaborative Filtering (CF). We study two Last FM listening events datasets, LFM-1b [7] and the earlier constructed Celma’s LFM-360k [8] alongside the recently proposed metric of *bias disparity* [9] to assess user gender preference distortion with reference to a baseline comparison in a user’s listening histories.

1.3 Structure of the Report

We structure this report as follows: Section 2 presents a review of the state of the art, contextualising our work within the MIR, mRS and Gender Studies research fields. Section 3 presents the methodology and experimental design to assess gender bias propagation offline. Section 4 presents the results obtained for the OSA assessment of a gender bias alongside a discussion of our findings. The paper concludes with section 5 where our findings are once again, concluded and contextualised followed by a proposal of future work - within and outside the scope of this project.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

We structure this section as follows: Section 2.1 details historical implications in MIR, firstly focusing on the state of the art perspective of MIR as a *socio-technical artefact* and secondly, considering means in which gender has been considered within the field. In section 2.2, we present a brief overview of RS and mRS, detailing commonly deployed filtering methodologies, literature exploring the role of social influence (including gender) in RS and finally, commonly deployed accuracy, beyond-accuracy and bias measures.

2.1 Social Implications in MIR

Research on mRS exists within the wider academic context of MIR, a broad research field which aims to resolve user music information requirements by deploying content based methods in combination with Information Retrieval (IR) methodologies (such as statistics and probability theory) [10]. With the formation of the field's main conference, the International Society on Music Information Retrieval (ISMIR) taking place as early as the year 2000, MIR remains a relatively novel research field for which much social growth and development can be observed. In this chapter, we first centre our attention towards social and ethical implications surrounding MIR, subsequently narrowing our scope to consider how the field has considered Gender Studies, the interdisciplinary academic field which this work borders.

2.1.1 MIR as a Socio-technical Artifact

Figure 2: Diagram showing the relations between the different sections of current MIR research identified in *Roadmap for Music Information Research* [11]

Over the past decade, the perspective of MIR as the study of a neutral artefact has become less common practice with researchers now acknowledging the potential for one's social fingerprint to be embedded in system architectures. As detailed by Holzapfel et al. [12], recent years have given rise to the growing perspective of MIR as a socio-technical artifact whereby the potential for both studied and developed systems to *'...not exist as an object in isolation, but instead as a combination of human arrangement, technical artefacts and social practices.'* [13] is acknowledged. In Xavier et al.'s *Roadmap for Music Information Research* [11], a holistic overview of future research directions for the MIR field, such viewpoints are reiterated. As shown in Figure 2, Xavier et al. frame socio-technical ethics through the lens of the socio-cultural perspective (one of the several fundamental taxonomies of MIR research) highlighting the importance of a multidisciplinary, social perspective widely held to this day in the field of MIR.

Whilst the socio-technical perspective can provide a more holistic, complex model of the bi-directional interplay between an individual, society and an MIR system, it is

also crucial to consider unpremeditated impact which may arise as a result of such added complexity. Forms of bias are one means in which undesired functionality can be both embedded and transpire at various stages of a computer systems life cycle. In the works of Friedman’s ‘*Bias in Computer Systems*’ [14], three discrete categories of bias are identified to commonly emerge in system architectures:

1. *Pre-existing bias*: This can emerge when biases are embedded which exist independently of a system. This type of bias is said to emerge at both a societal level (for example through social institutions, practices and attitudes) and also at an individual level where personal biases may be imposed. Consider the example of an institution who’s MIR research team has many industrial connections with western companies in the field, established over many years. Research may thus, also follow a direction which disproportionately represents western musical culture due to the institution’s profit driven incentives (i.e. maintaining funding by continuing to exclusively collaborate on future projects).
2. *Technical-bias*: This can arise as a product of both technical considerations and constraints. For example, in the recent works of Flexer et al. [15], the issue of technical bias was highlighted within the context of mRS such that so called *hub-songs* located in the main cluster of songs mapped to a higher dimensional space were identified to be recommended a disproportionate amount of times to users despite them holding little semantic value.
3. *Emergent bias*: This arises through a user’s use of software in manners in which the developer did not intend. This is said to typically arise as a product of societal changes some time after the development of the system.

Whilst not explicit to MIR, it is interesting to consider that the above biases are also identified in the pivotal ISMIR tutorial on ethics in 2014 [16] emphasising their applicability to be applied to both our research on gender distribution in mRS and MIR as a broader discipline. In our work, we will consider such biases extensively. Firstly, when we discretely categorise artist gender in the LFM-1b dataset, a concept

widely considered to be a product of society's influence [17] and thus, (at least partially) a social construction. To impose discrete categorisation upon what is considered by some to be a continuous spectrum, requires both valid justifications for such design choices and thus, a good understanding of the issues surrounding the field of gender studies (see Gender Studies in MIR). Secondly, we will consider such biases extensively when reasoning about the conditions under which CF methodologies tested may propagate a gender bias (if found).

2.1.2 Gender Studies in MIR

Inline with the state of the art perspective of MIR as a socio-technical artefact, the role of gender has been evidenced at both an *organic* (absent of algorithmic influence) [18] and *algorithmic level* [2, 4] to influence an individual's music preference. Before discussing such literature further (see Section 2.2.2) we first outline the field of Gender Studies to provide further contextualisation.

The field of *Gender Studies* is now a widely researched academic discipline with philosophers such as Simone de Beauvoir [19] pioneering the movement to redefine and subsequently, articulate gender and sex differences from a Feminist perspective. Since then, researchers from both natural and social sciences have worked to develop and further understand the notion of what constitutes and furthermore, differentiates the two theories of sex and gender. Sadly, current research relating to gender within the field of MIR often does little to differentiate between the two definitions, frequently (incorrectly) using the two terms interchangeably. Although related and somewhat intertwined, the two definitions are fundamentally different and thus, using the two terms interchangeably is both wrong and problematic. To understand this concept further we consider two widely accepted definitions of gender and sex as defined in [20].

Definition 2.1 "*Sex*" is a theory about human beings which divides them into two biologically based categories, - male or female.

Definition 2.2 "*Gender*" is a culturally variable elaboration of sex, as a hierarchical pair (where male is code superior and female inferior).

As reiterated in [21], a wealth of works differentiates gender from sex as being socially as opposed to biologically constructed leading to the notion of *gendered identities*. Although arguably differentiable, the two definitions are also often argued to be systematically intertwined by the likes of Judith Butler in her highly influential work *Gender Troubles* [17]. Butler argues that many deployments of gender actually serve to essentialise sex, which in itself, is said to be socially constructed through routine gendered performances. Butler argues this application therefore works to unsettle the binary logic of sex itself and the two definitions of gender and sex begin to converge.

Whilst it is evident that the two theories are highly interrelated, we consider our work a study of gender due to growing concern in popular media and academia that the music industry still shows symptoms of a male patriarchy - female artists still only account for less than a quarter of successful performers and an even smaller share of successful songwriters despite music consumption being approximately balanced across genders ¹.

We now discuss the issue of gender representation in datasets commonly used in MIR. By means of example, we outline Biven's work, '*The gender binary will not be deprogrammed: Ten years of coding gender on Facebook*' [22]. Although not directly related to MIR, many of the issues raised are highly translatable as later explained. Biven's work details how, on the 13 February 2014, Facebook extended their classification of user gender from binary to a more flexible definition which incorporated a third category, '*other*', in which a user could choose from 56 additional new options for gender. Although this additional functionality may appear to decompose the constructed binary values of gender therefore giving users more freedom, Biven argues that this is sadly not the case. Ultimately, gender is constrained to be three categories (male, female, custom) which, although not strictly binary, creates an

¹<http://assets.uscannenberg.org/docs/aai-inclusion-recording-studio-2019.pdf>

Name	Static	Gender (user/artist)	Non-binary (user/artist)
LFM-1b	yes	yes / no	no / no
Yahoo Music	yes	no / no	no / no
nowplaying	yes	no / MBid	no / yes
MuMu Dataset	yes	no / MBid	no / yes
Celma's Last.fm	yes	yes / MBid	no / yes
GroupLens Last.FM	yes	no / no	no / no
Million Song Dataset (MSD)	yes	no / MBid	no / yes
Million Musical Tweets Dataset	yes	no / MBid	no / yes
"Changing Their Tune" Dataset	yes	yes / no	no / no
KKBox's Music Recommendation	yes	yes / no	no / no
Million Song Dataset Artist (MSD-A)	yes	no / MBid	no / yes
The Music Listening Histories Dataset (MLHD)	yes	yes / MBid	no / yes

Table 1: Gender status of popular MIR datasets used in mRS research

over-simplified representation of gender which sits at the periphery of binary and non-binary values. Biven concludes that motivations for such design decisions are more often than not in the private sector, profit driven as companies amalgamate their product to satisfy ever changing stakeholders' needs. In MIR, commonly used datasets are similarly, often acquired through private companies such as Last-FM, Spotify and Deezer. Due to these companies often not classifying gender in a non-binary manner and additionally, a lack of current research at the intersection of MIR and Gender Studies, many commonly used datasets in research therefore have a lack of (if any) adequate gender classification - sadly also a constraint of this work.

Table 1. displays the gender status of common datasets used in mRS research compiled as a collective endeavor of the Music Technology Group, Barcelona ². From this data we observe a trend for the majority of datasets to contain no information about gender and even less to contain non-binary gender. We also observe a trend for commonly used MIR datasets such as the Million Song dataset [23] to simply provide a MusicBrainz id (MBid) for which gender can then be retrieved if so desired. We argue that this approach is not adequate to generate a representative picture of gender in MIR studies for two reasons: (1) Non-binary gender is represented

²<https://www.upf.edu/web/mtg>

in an overly simplistic manner by simply including an *other* category. (2) Gender representation is sparse with 46.5% of artists having no identified gender³. Such issues provide a motivation for this work whereby we first, compile, encode and classify artist gender in both the LFM-1b and LFM-360k datasets studied as detailed in Section 3. We note that limitations of our approach are several, discussed in further detail in Section 5.

2.2 Recommender Systems

Whilst our research will focus on the study of mRS, it is also appropriate to consider the more general scope of literature on RS as many of the principle algorithms deployed are both translatable and highly applicable to the music domain. RS, deriving from Information Systems, are designed to produce personalised, meaningful recommendations of items to a user base. With the rise of ‘*big data*’ systems, the issue of constructing a meaningful system architecture for a user to interface becomes a pressing issue for users and providers alike. To understand this further, we consider the basic settings under which one can formally define the RS problem space. Formal definitions have been defined in various manners, however we will outline the formal notation widely accepted by the RS community as defined by Adomavicius and Tuzhilin in their paper ‘*Toward the Next Generation of Recommender Systems: A Survey of the State-of-the-Art and Possible Extensions*’ [24].

Let \mathcal{U} be a set of users and J be a set of items. Let g be a utility function that measures the usefulness of item j to a user u i.e. $g : \mathcal{U} \times J \rightarrow R$ where R is a totally ordered set. We define the problem space such that, for each user $u \in \mathcal{U}$, we want to choose items $j' \in J$ that maximizes a user’s utility i.e.

$$\forall u \in \mathcal{U}, i^{\max, u} = \arg \max_{i \in J} g(u, i) \quad (2.1)$$

To maximise user utility, a common approach is to deploy filtering algorithms, of which there are four traditional recommendation methods: [25]:

³<https://musicbrainz.org/statistics>

Demographic Filtering (DF): uses demographic information (such as gender, age, etc.) to identify user types which show a preference for items and then uses this to generate recommendations appropriately. [25].

Content-based filtering (CBF): forms recommendations by analysing item descriptions (i.e. the *semantic attributes* [26]) that have been rated by the user and the description of items which are to be recommended. Content-based recommendations can also be used at a lower level to generate recommendations based on the content of the items being recommended. Following the formalisation defined in [24], we can define CBF such that utility $g(u, j)$ is based upon the utilities $g(u, j_i)$, which are assigned by users to ‘*similar*’ items $j_i \in J$. The concept of an item’s characteristics can be more formally defined through the idea of item-profile, a set of attributes which characterise an item in the system.

Collaborative Filtering (CF): proposed by Goldberg et al. in early research exploring automatic filtering for electronic mail [27], takes as input a set of user ratings for a user base, and outputs a prediction of a user rating for a given item. This prediction is formed by considering other users who are deemed ‘*similar*’ using a similarity measure such as the commonly deployed Vector Cosine-Based Similarity and Correlation-Based Similarity which utilises Pearson correlation measures [28]. Ratings can be generated both implicitly (e.g. play counts in the LFM-1b dataset), and explicitly through rankings (e.g. user rankings of movies in the MovieLens dataset [29]). CF methodologies can be discreetly categorised into two classes, namely:

1. *Memory based Approaches:* use the entire, or sometimes a sample of the *user-item* matrix to generate item predictions for a given user. Here, two methodologies are typically deployed, *user-item* and *item-item* approaches. *User-item* filtering takes as input a user u , finds users that are similar to that user based on the *similarity* of ratings $u_i \in U$, and recommends items that those similar users liked. *Item-item* filtering takes as input an item i , finds users who liked that item, and finds other items that those users or similar users also liked. Common memory based approaches deployed in the state of the art in-

clude neighbourhood-based CF (historically the most popular recommendation methodology deployed [30]) and Item-based/user-based top-N CF [28]. Whilst memory based approaches for CF remains an active research area, there are several limitations for memory based techniques, such as the fact that sparsity in data can lead to few common items between users. To overcome such issues, *model-based* approaches have subsequently been proposed.

2. *Model based Approaches*: typically provide more accurate predictions for sparse data and thus, are commonly implemented in state of the art systems for which the *user-item* matrix is very large. Model based approaches are also often considered to be more scalable and thus, more desirable when working with big data. In comparison, memory based approaches require the computation of similarity between a user and all neighbours which in practice, can be a very costly procedure. Model based approaches reduce this execution time by deriving off-line models of the data to predict on-line ratings more efficiently [31]. When working with Model based RS, it is first necessary to optimise the *hyper-parameters* of the model, achieved in the learning phase before recommendations are output. One commonly adopted model to implement RS is the latent factor model (LFM). LFM applies a dimensionality reduction by factorising the (often sparse) *user-item* rating matrix into lower order matrices, the user feature and item feature matrix. State of the art algorithms which utilise this approach include SVD [32], matrix factorisation (MF) [33] and NMF [34]. For a more detailed overview of model based approaches (in particular matrix factorisation) we refer to the work of Chen et al. [35].

In our work, we apply a range of both memory and model based approaches to provide a holistic overview of common CF methodologies deployed in state of the art mRS. We explore the degree to which such methodologies differ in the extent to which disproportionate gender treatment might propagate in item recommendations lists.

Our research focuses exclusively on CF algorithms. We justify the importance of focusing on CF in our work for the historic value of their application to mRS,

(one of the first applications of CF was to the music domain as detailed in ‘*Social Information Filtering: Algorithms for Automating "Word of Mouth"*’[36]) and their current prominence (particularly with respect to model based approaches) in state of the art mRS.

Hybrid Filtering: approaches use a combination of collaborative and content-based filtering or, collaborative and demographic filtering to generate recommendations for a user base. These are more commonly applied in state of the art RS deployed in industry.

2.2.1 Music Recommender Systems

Music Recommender Systems are a subdivision of RS whereby the items being recommended consist of musical content. With the cross cultural advent of music streaming platforms in the past decade ^{4 5 6 7}, mRS have become vital tools to reduce *choice overload* and further elicit personalisation for music listeners [37]. Whilst many similarities can be observed in comparison to other RS domains (such as the underlying filtering algorithms deployed), mRS are unique for a multitude of reasons for which we highlight the most relevant to this work.

Foremost, state of the art mRS research often places a strong focus on the multi-disciplinary approach to resolve *user-item* requirements. Specifically, we outline 3 state of the art mRS disciplines which draw from a diverse range of research fields as highlighted in the works of Schedl et al. [38] - *Psychological based, Situation based and Culture aware mRS*.

Psychological based mRS is a growing research field which draws upon psychological works on the effect of music on emotion and personality. Within the context of Psychological based mRS, emotions are typically mapped to represent a listeners short term music preferences and personality to long term listening preferences.

⁴<https://www.businessinsider.es/youtube-user-statistics-2018-5?IR=Tr=US2>

⁵<https://investors.spotify.com/financials/press-release-details/2018/Spotify-Technology-SA-Announces-Financial-Results-for-First-Quarter-2018>

⁶<https://www.menabytes.com/anghami-21-million-mau>

⁷<https://technode.com/2017/06/23/top-5-chinese-music-apps-in-2017>

With respect to personality, user information can be gathered implicitly through analysing user characteristics or explicitly (for example by asking a user to fill out a form of typical dimensions used to assess personality types). Such data can then be used in various manners to aid recommendations. One means in which this is typically achieved is by using user personality dimensions to find other similar users to generate item recommendations using a neighbourhood based CF approach. Another common approach used is to directly transfer personality dimensions to latent factors for matrix factorisation based approaches. With respect to emotion, the task of utilising this characteristic in a mRS is three fold: (1) Infer the emotion of a user, achieved implicitly or explicitly. (2) Infer the emotion of the music to be recommended. This task belongs to the research domain of Music Emotion Recognition (MER) for which many novel solutions have been proposed. (3) Compute relations across user and music emotions to subsequently generate more personalised and meaningful item recommendations. With respect to psychological based mRS, a wealth of preliminary works exist with such approaches now becoming more popularised in recent years. Notably, the role of user emotions was directly considered in the works of Deng et al. [39] where emotion aware methodology based on CF was deployed. In more recent years, Shen et al. [40] have formalised both the concept of emotions and personality under the notion of short and long term music preferences respectively. In their work, they deploy a deep framework, the PEIA model, to learn user-music correlations on personality and emotion data gathered via multi-facet feature extraction from data from the popular social media platform, WeChat.

Situation based mRS is another popular research field currently gaining traction in recent years. In conventional mRS, typically two signals are considered to generate recommendations: item and user signals. In situation based mRS, the facet of signals considered is widely extended with the overall goal of generating more personalised item recommendations by considering contextual information which may otherwise be lost by just considering listening events. Such additional signals are commonly referred to as situational signals and can incorporate data such as location, time activity, weather mood and social context. In recent years, such approaches have

been widely studied [41, 42, 43, 44] with great success however Schedl et al. [38] critiques such applications for being lacking in the use of a multi-facet of situational signals.

Culture aware based mRS are mRS which deploy knowledge about a user's culture specific background to produce more meaningful item recommendations. Whilst an abundance of work exists which shows the effect of cultural dimensions on user listening preferences there currently exists minimal work applying such knowledge to the field of mRS. In recent years we highlight that one such application was made by Schedl et al. in their publication *User Models for Culture-Aware Music Recommendation: Fusing Acoustic and Cultural Cues* [45]. In their research, a user model is proposed to model cultural aspects which may influence user listening preferences. These are then utilised as contextual information when generating item recommendations with the LFM-1b dataset. Results from Schedl et al.'s work show that their model is able to outperform other recommendation models which only incorporate musical or culture information. Such findings suggest that the use of cultural information in mRS may be a crucial component to generate more personalised and subsequently meaningful item recommendations.

Another means in which mRS can be differentiated from other RS domains is through its user level impact. Schedl [46] argues that the consumption of information on mRS based platforms is distinctly unique to other RS domains exposing potential differences in *algorithmic* influence which may arise. For example, consumption time between items in the music domain is said to be far shorter than in other RS domains. Consequently, users may take less time to form opinions about items which may impact upon *algorithmic influence* playing a more substantial role in distorting music preference.

With regard to how mRS influence may transpire, we highlight one impact highly relevant to this work - *diversity distortion*. This refers to the scenario where recommended music diversity is modified with reference to an organic comparison - translated to our work as a distortion in the proportion of recommended artist genders. At a user level, this can translate to a distortion of music preference and sub-

sequently, music consumption behaviours being modified. Literature on the means in which *diversity distortion* may arise is conflicting in the sense that two polarising viewpoints have been seen to emerge.

At one end of the spectrum, mRS have been evidenced to expand the diversity of a user's music consumption, exposing genres and content which a user may not previously have been subject to. Datta et al. [47] show that the diversity of music which a user consumes is increased by algorithmic recommendation. Similarly, in the movie domain, Nguyen et al. [48] show that users who adopt item recommendations experience higher genre diversity with respect to those who do not. The temporal effects of music recommendation have also been studied. In the works of Anderson et al. [49] the diversity of a user's listening behaviour is found to increase with time due to consumption behaviours shifting more towards *organic* as opposed to *algorithmic* influence.

Notwithstanding, concern as arisen regarding the extent to which mRS may conversely, limit diversity, over-exposing users to agreeable content which reinforces pre-existing music preferences - a phenomena widely known as a *filter bubble* as popularised by Pariser [50]. Translated to our work, we trace how mRS expand or reinforce a user's *organic* gender bias entering the system as a form of pre-existing bias.

2.2.2 The Role of Social Influence in RS

At an *organic level* an individual's preference for music has been shown to be at least partially socially determined. Rentfrow and Gosling [51] show a user's preference for a given song to be affected by a multi-facet of social factors for which several patterns linking music preferences with personality dimensions, self-views and cognitive abilities are identified. More recently, the role of gender has also been shown to have an affect on user listening music preferences as shown by Milar et al. in their paper *Selective hearing: gender bias in the music preferences of young adults* [18]. In Millar's work, the existence of a gender bias in the music preferences of undergraduates between the age of 18-25 is explored through applying a qualitative,

questionnaire based methodology. Findings show that there are significant differences between male and female gender listening preferences which Millar argues are enough to warrant subsequent research on the field. The paper demonstrates how user listening preferences are influenced by a multitude of factors highly dependent on group biases which can emerge both at an institutional and societal level. Such gender biases can also have substantial impact upon a user's reaction to music recommendation. In the works of McEnnis et al.'s *Sociology and music recommendation systems* [52], the same recommended song is evidenced to be interpreted differently by those who have experienced different social influence. If one considers gender to be a social construction as suggested by the likes of Butler [17], gender is also clearly implied by McEnnis work to influence one's reaction to music recommendation.

At an *algorithmic level*, the impact of gender (both at a user and artist level) have been widely considered in literature through the perspective of proportional treatment for which we highlight the most relevant to this work. Ekstrand et al. [4] examined gender distribution of item recommendations in the book RS domain. Findings showed that commonly deployed CF differ in the gender distributions of generated item recommendation lists such that nearest neighbour based approaches were shown to proportionality reflect users item preferences in their reading histories whereas model based matrix factorisation were found to offer minimal reflection of *user-item* preferences, instead favoring books whose author was of male gender. In the music domain, Aguiar et al. [2] have studied gender proportion in song recommendations on the popular music streaming platform, Spotify. Agiar et al. deploy a methodology they coin '*conditioning on observables*' to assess the extent to which artists ranked in the New Music Friday playlist are affected by gender after accounting for plausible determinants of inclusion on playlists such as country, song characteristics (e.g. bpm, key signature) and past streaming success. Results find that there is some evidence consistent with the presence of bias (both for and against female artists) however the paper does not draw subsequent relations between this and the disproportionate low streaming share of female artists on the platform. In recent years, Ekstrand et al. [4] have studied the effect of commonly deployed recommendation algorithms on the utility for users of different gender groups. Ekstrand

et al. find that both the ML1M and LFM1K datasets studied show statistically significant differences in effectiveness across gender groups. Interestingly, their paper also highlights that users who are women on the Last.FM platform typically receive higher accuracy recommendations despite lower representation of female users in both datasets studied. Such work highlights that recommendation does not in all cases, exclusively benefit a majority group. This implies that there may be other underlying *user-item* configurations which influence recommendation accuracy, a topic of further exploration in this work. To address such issues of disproportionate gender treatment which may arise in RS recommendations, Edizel et al. [3] have recently proposed a novel means of mitigating the derivation of so called *sensitive features* (such as gender) in the latent space. In their work they propose a fairness constraint based on the predictability of *sensitive features*. To achieve this, they propose a new algorithm FaiRecSys that mitigates *algorithmic bias* by post-processing the recommendation matrix with minimum impact on the utility of recommendations provided to the end-users.

2.2.3 Accuracy Measures

To evaluate the performance of a mRS, accuracy metrics are often applied. In the following section we outline a sample accuracy metrics detailed by Schedl et al. [38] to be commonly deployed in state of the art RS research.

Mean absolute error (MAE) is one of the most common metrics used to assess error/accuracy of recommender algorithms. MAE computes the absolute deviation between predicted and actual rankings assessing how close predicted ratings are to actual user ratings. MAE is computed in the following way:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{r_{u,i} \in T} |r_{u,i} - \hat{r}_{u,i}| \quad (2.2)$$

where $r_{u,i}$ and $\hat{r}_{u,i}$ denote actual and predicted ratings respectively for an item i and user u in test set T .

Root mean square error (RMSE) is an error/accuracy metric which extends MAE, squaring the error term to further penalise bigger differences between predicted and actual ratings.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{r_{u,i} \in T} (r_{u,i} - \hat{r}_{u,i})^2} \quad (2.3)$$

Precision at top K recommendations (P@K) is a metric to assess the accuracy for recommending relevant items. To compute P@K we consider for each user the top K items recommended whose ratings appear in the test set T are considered. Formally, we define P@K as follows:

$$P_u@K = \frac{|L_u \cap \hat{L}_u|}{|\hat{L}_u|} \quad (2.4)$$

where T and \hat{L}_u denote the recommended set of size K for which each item $i \in K$ have the highest predicted ratings. Globally, we can then compute P@K by averaging over $P_u@K$ all users in T.

Mean average precision at top K recommendations (MAP@K) is a rank based metric to assess the accuracy of a recommendation. The metric computes the overall precision at different lengths of recommendation lists produced. MAP is computed as the mean of average precision over the entire set of users in a test set. Formally, we define the Average precision at the top K recommendations (AP@K) as follows:

$$AP@K = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^K P@i \cdot \text{rel}(i) \quad (2.5)$$

where $\text{rel}(i) = 1$ if the i th recommendation is relevant and 0 otherwise and N is defined to be the number of relevant items.

Normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG) is a metric used to measure ranking quality of a list of recommended items now commonly deployed in the evaluation of mRS [53, 54, 55]. Formally, the metric is defined as follows:

$$DCG_u = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{r_{u,i}}{\log_2(i+1)} \quad (2.6)$$

where recommendations for a user u are sorted according to predicted values in descending order. $r_{u,i}$ is defined to be the true rating of an item i for user u in the test set T , and N to be the length of the recommendation list. To compare DCG across a user base, normalisation is applied by computing the ideal DCG for a user u . Formally, we compute the normalised discounted cumulative gain for a user u as follows:

$$NDCG_u = \frac{DCG_u}{IDCG_u} \quad (2.7)$$

Overall $NDCG$ is then computed by averaging all $NDCG_u$ values across a user set.

Half-life utility (HLU) is a ranking aware accuracy measure. Originating in the fields of information retrieval and machine learning, the metric is now also commonly applied to evaluate the utility of a recommendation list in mRS. The metric is based on the assumption that the probability of selecting an item in a recommendation list exponentially decays with respect to an item's position in the ranking. Formally HLU for a user u as follows:

$$HLU_u = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\max(r_{u,i} - d, 0)}{2^{(rank_{u,i}-1)/(h-1)}} \quad (2.8)$$

where $r_{u,i}$ and $rank_{u,i}$ denote rating and rank of item i for user u respectively. N is the length of recommendation list and d represents a default rating. The half-time h is computed as the rank of an item in the list such that a user will listen to with a probability of 50%. Normalisation can be applied by dividing by the maximum utility to compare HLU_i across users. An overall HLU can then be computed by averaging HLU_i values across all users in a user set.

Mean percentile rank (MPR) is a ranking aware based metric which is computed as the average of percentile rank, PR_u for each user. Formally, PR_u for a user u is defined as follows:

$$PR_u = \frac{\sum_{r_{u,i} \in T} r_{u,i} \cdot rank_{u,i}}{\sum_{r_{u,i} \in T} r_{u,i}}$$

where $r_{u,i}$ is the rating of item i by user u in the test set T and $rank_{u,i}$ is defined to be the percentile rank of item i within an ordered list of recommendations for user

u . MPR is then computed as the mean of PR_u across all users in a user set.

2.2.4 Beyond-Accuracy Measures

In addition, beyond-accuracy measures are now also commonly used to evaluate RS performance in aspects which accuracy measures alone cannot capture. These will be utilized in our work to trace the cause of a *bias disparity* after CF music recommendation. Again, we refer to Schedl et al.'s work for a more detailed elaboration of each algorithm.

Spread is a beyond-accuracy metric used to assess the extent to which a recommender algorithm can represent a large set of items. Formally spread is defined as follows:

$$\text{spread} = - \sum_{i \in I} P(i) \log P(i) \quad (2.9)$$

where I represents the set of all items, $P(i) = \text{count}(i) / \sum_{i' \in I} \text{count}(i')$ where $\text{count}(i)$ is the number of times item i appeared in recommendation lists.

Coverage: is a metric used to assess proportion of items which the recommendation algorithm is able to recommend. Formally, the metric is defined as follows:

$$\text{coverage} = \frac{|\hat{T}|}{|T|} \quad (2.10)$$

where $|T|$ is the size of the test set and $|\hat{T}|$ is the number of ratings in T for which the system is able to predict a value.

Novelty is used to assess a RS ability to recommend new items to a user who did not previously know about the item. Formally, Novelty is defined as:

$$\text{novelty} = \frac{1}{|U|} \sum_{u \in U} \sum_{i \in L_u} \frac{-\log_2 \text{pop}_i}{N} \quad (2.11)$$

where pop_i is the popularity of item i computed as the proportion of users who rated item i . L_u is the list of the top N recommendations for a user u . When computing novelty it is assumed that the probability of a user selecting a previously known

item is proportional to the item’s global popularity.

Serendipity measures a recommender systems ability to suggest relevant and surprising items. Formally, the general definition of Serendipity is defined as:

$$\text{serendipity } (L_u) = \frac{|L_u^{unexp} \cap L_u^{useful}|}{|L_u|} \quad (2.12)$$

where L_u^{unexp} and L_u^{useful} denote subsets of the recommendation list for a user u , L_u such that items are unexpected and useful respectively. Methodologies to assess usefulness can vary with one commonly utilised means being to take user ratings as a proxy. Unexpectedness is measured by computing a distance measure (such as the cosine measure) between items which are expected.

Diversity is a metric used to assess the degree to which recommended items differ from each other. Whilst the metric can be defined in various manners, one common definition is:

$$\text{diversity } (L) = \frac{\sum_{i \in L} \sum_{j \in L \setminus i} \text{dist}_{i,j}}{|L| \cdot (|L| - 1)} \quad (2.13)$$

where $\text{dist}_{i,j}$ between items i and j is a distance function such as cosine similarity, inverse Pearson Correlation or Hamming distance.

2.2.5 Bias Measures for RS

In recent years, the notion of bias has been extensively explored in the RS domain, both at a consumer and provider level. Bias metrics typically aim to capture *relative bias* (i.e. bias pre-existing in data, for example user listening histories in LFM-1b) and *algorithmic bias* (e.g. how filtering algorithms can result in unfair item and user treatment) to measure disproportionate *unfair* treatment of a *protected group*.

One of the most well studied biases in RS literature is *popularity bias*, with the music domain being no exception to this phenomenon [8, 56]. This describes the scenario in which popular items are recommended frequently (in some cases disproportionately) while the majority of other items in the *long-tail* (unpopular items) do not get proportional attention. With respect to provider fairness, such issues have been

well studied and frequently highlighted in literature as a prominent issue for CF algorithms [57, 58]. In more recent years, *popularity bias* has also been considered from a user perspective, showing that accuracy and calibration of user recommendations may be substantially worsened for user groups who do not favor popular items [59, 60]. In the works of Kowaland et al.[60], the notion of *popularity bias* was considered at a consumer level on the LFM-1b dataset studied in our work. Kowland et al. find that a user group listening to largely unpopular artists are more likely to receive worse recommendations by CF (in the sense that accuracy of recommendations is lower) showing how *popularity bias* can have an effect on recommendation accuracy in the LFM-1b dataset. In the works of Ferraro et al. [61], the effect of musical styles with respect to popularity bias has been studied. Findings show that the Matrix Factorisation based CF approach studied increases users' exposure to popular musical styles and furthermore reduces their exposure to the long-tail items thus, showing support for the existence of *popularity bias* in state of the art CF algorithms. In recent years, the metric of *Bias Disparity* has been commonly deployed to assess group bias propagation across user and item categories. Formally, we outline the metric defined in [62] as follows:

Preference ratio (PR). Let U be the set of n users, I be the set of m items and S be the $n \times m$ input matrix, where $S(u, i) = 1$ if user u has selected item i , and zero otherwise. Given matrix S , the input preference ratio for user group G on item category C is the fraction of liked items by group G in category C , formally defined as the following:

$$PR_S(G, C) = \frac{\sum_{u \in G} \sum_{i \in C} S(u, i)}{\sum_{u \in G} \sum_{i \in I} S(u, i)} \quad (2.14)$$

Bias disparity (BD). It is defined to be the relative difference between the preference bias for input S and output of a recommendation algorithm R . Formally we define the metric as the following:

$$BD(G, C) = \frac{PR_R(G, C) - PR_S(G, C)}{PR_S(G, C)} \quad (2.15)$$

First applied to the RS domain by Tsintzou et al. [9], the metric has recently gained

a lot of traction in its application to multiple RS domains. In the works of Lin et al. [62] *bias disparity* is applied to measure the extent to which state of the art CF algorithms can exacerbate pre-existing biases in the MovieLens dataset [29]. Their findings show significant differentiations in bias propagation across memory and model based CF algorithms, such that they observe a trend for memory based nearest neighbour based approaches to show similarities with baseline popularity based algorithms whereas such patterns are not observed in model based approaches. Such findings raise questions with regards to the relation between *gender* and *popularity bias* which we further aim to explore in this work.

Chapter 3

Methods

In this exploratory study, we focus on the measurement of *bias disparity* in RS, defined as "[...] *the case where the recommender system introduces bias in the data, by amplifying existing biases and reinforcing stereotypes.*" [9].

Building on existing literature [9, 62, 63], we first reproduce the study presented by Lin et al. [62], in which preference bias amplification in collaborative recommendation is analysed using the MovieLens dataset [29], a dataset of user activity with a movie recommendation system. In our work, we focus on the music domain making use of two Last.fm¹ listening event datasets publicly available: 1) Celma's LFM-360k dataset [8]; 2) Schedl's LFM-1b dataset [7]. Our goal is twofold: on one hand, reproducing and verifying whether previous results [62] hold across different datasets. On the other hand, we aim at highlighting which aspects specific to the music domain can be extracted by this analysis, connecting with existing literature on gender bias in music preferences [18, 64].

¹<https://www.last.fm>

3.1 The LFM-1b Dataset

The LFM-1b dataset consists of more than one billion listening events created by over 120,000 users of the music streaming platform Last.fm [7]. In our analysis, we consider user-artist playcounts formed by aggregating user-song listening events by common artists. We then scale logarithmically the number of listens, as done in [65, 66].

	LFM-1b		LFM-360k	
	<i>male</i>	<i>female</i>	<i>male</i>	<i>female</i>
Users	31.4K	11.5K	94.3K	30.8K
%	<i>71.67</i>	<i>28.33</i>	<i>75.40</i>	<i>24.60</i>
Artists	127K	27.3K	50.4K	10.5K
%	<i>82.30</i>	<i>17.70</i>	<i>82.83</i>	<i>17.17</i>
Top-head	25.7K	4.8K	10.1K	1.5K
%	<i>85.21</i>	<i>15.79</i>	<i>86.99</i>	<i>13.01</i>
Long-tail	100K	22.2K	38.7K	8.5K
%	<i>81.87</i>	<i>18.13</i>	<i>81.95</i>	<i>18.05</i>

Table 2: Users’ and artists’ distributions after filtering process. “Top-head” artists are the top 20% of artists by play counts, while the remaining 80% are the “long-tail.”

We work with a filtered version of the dataset in which: a) we remove users who listened to less than 10 unique artists, and artists listened to by less than 10 users; b) we discard users whose listening history contains more than 25% of artists with unknown gender, to mitigate the impact of artists with missing gender in the dataset.

User gender is represented in the dataset with three categories: *male*, *female* and *N/A*. We choose to focus only on users with self-declared gender, working with two final categories of user gender: male and female. As shown in Table 2, distributions are highly imbalanced towards men – 72% of the users are men. Artist gender is not represented in the LFM-1b dataset, consequently we retrieve this information from the open music encyclopedia MusicBrainz² (MB) [67]. Code repositories to implement the following approach are made openly available³ alongside the acquired

²<https://musicbrainz.org/>

³<https://github.com/dshakes90/LFM-1b-MusicBrainz-Gender-Wrangler>

LFM-1b				
No.	Male artist	Plays	Female artist	Plays
1	Radiohead	2.6M	Lana Del Rey	1.2M
2	The Beatles	2.5M	Lady Gaga	1.1M
3	Pink Floyd	2.1M	Rihanna	0.8M
4	Daft Punk	2.0M	Björk	0.7M
5	Metallica	1.9M	Madonna	0.6M
LFM-360k				
No.	Male artist	Plays	Female artist	Plays
1	Radiohead	6.2M	Björk	1.3M
2	The Beatles	5.4M	Avril Lavigne	1.1M
3	In Flames	4.9M	Madonna	1.1M
4	Metallica	4.3M	Britney Spears	0.9M
5	Muse	4.2M	Regina Spektor	0.9M

Table 3: Top 5 artists ordered by total play counts in LFM-1b and LFM-360k datasets.

results of the data wrangling⁴ to elicit reproducibility . We identify five discrete categories of gender defined in the MB database: *male*, *female*, *other*, *N/A* and *undef*. In the case of artists of gender *N/A* and *undef*, these are differentiated by artists for which gender is not applicable and identifiable respectively. For bands, we compute gender counts of all members and then compute an overall classification based on whichever count has a majority. In the case of artists with gender ties (e.g, a band consisting of 2 males and 2 females), we discard such artists from our final analysis as gender is in this instance, deemed ambiguous. After applying this methodology, we are able to identify 27% of artists with a known-gender. Distributions are observed to be highly imbalanced such that artists of male gender consist of the majority (82%) of artists for which gender can be identified, as shown in Table 2.

In our final analysis, we further filter artists not identified as male or female according to the procedure described above. Artists of gender *other* are discarded as we deem such data to be too sparse to be informative in the analysis of users' listening preferences. We note this group merits further future evaluation, perhaps relying on qualitative methods, and limitations of this binary approach are discussed in Section

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/3964506.XyE5N0FKg5n>

5. Table 3 presents the top 5 artists based on the total sum of play counts in the filtered LFM-1b dataset. We observe a trend for male artists' popularity, having approximately twice as much play counts as top-rated female artists/bands. We also observe a trend for the top male artists on the platform to be more commonly composed of bands in comparison to the top-rated female artists.

3.2 The LFM-360k Dataset

The LFM-360k dataset [8] consists of approximately 360,000 users' listening histories from Last.fm collected during Fall 2008, presenting a snapshot of listening activity for an earlier period in comparison to the LFM-1b dataset. With respect to user gender distributions the proportion of users with a self-declared gender rises to 91% whereas similarly to the LFM-1b dataset, artist gender is not defined. To resolve this, we implement the same pre-processing methodology with the MB database as described for the LFM-1b dataset. After further applying the filtering criteria previously detailed, we are able to identify 31% of artists with a known gender, a proportion notably higher than that of what we were able to identify for the LFM-1b dataset. As presented in Table 2, artist gender distributions in the filtered dataset are once again highly imbalanced towards artists classified as men. For users with identified gender, we again observe a high imbalance towards male users (75%) comparable to rates observed in the LFM-1b dataset. When comparing the two datasets we observe several additional differences and similarities which may impact the propagation of a gender bias in artist recommendations. First, the number of users is significantly larger than that of the LFM-1b, whilst the number of artists is much smaller. Second, sparsity is higher in the LFM-360k dataset in comparison to the LFM-1b. Third, with regard to the top 5 artists of male and female gender in the dataset we observe significantly higher playcounts for artists classified as male in comparison to the LFM-1b dataset, as shown in Table 2. With regard to similarities across the two datasets, we observe that top 5 popular male artists are more commonly bands in comparison to the top 5 female artists. In addition, we observe that the long-tail of both datasets contains significantly higher distribution

of female artists, in comparison to the top head reinforcing the conclusion that female artists are significantly more likely to be less popular on the Last.fm platform and more likely to be proportionally less recommended as a result of this popularity bias.

3.3 Evaluation Metrics

In this section, we outline the metrics of *preference ratio*, *bias disparity*, alongside accuracy and beyond-accuracy considered during evaluation. A brief justification for the choice of each metric is also provided.

Bias Disparity (*BD*). To capture the tendency for CF algorithms to distort a user’s artist gender preference in generated recommendation lists we deploy the metrics *preference ratio* and *bias disparity* formally outlined in Section 2.2.5.

Accuracy and beyond-accuracy metrics. To evaluate mRS performance and trace the bi-directional influence of gender, we deploy two accuracy metrics: *Precision*, *nDCG*, and three beyond-accuracy metrics: *coverage*, *spread* and *long-tail percentage*. We refer to the metrics formulation as detailed in the work by Noia et al. [68].

Precision ($p@n$) captures the proportion of relevant items in top-N recommendations, such that relevance is a binary function that represents the relevance of item i for a user u . In our work, we consider relevant a recommendation which is greater or equal to the average scaled listening count for a user, after discarding outliers computed using the interquartile range. Although $p@n$ is useful for analysing generated item recommendations, it does not capture accuracy aspects relating to the rank of a recommendation. Hence, in our work we also deploy *nDCG*, a rank sensitive accuracy metric. With respect to metrics beyond accuracy, we utilise both *spread* and *coverage* to capture a RS ability to recommend a broad range of unique items. Such approaches are important to consider in our work to potentially reason and explain bias propagation across artist genders. The metric *long-tail percentage* is used to capture the proportion of item recommendations which exist in the long tail. In our work, we define the long tail as the 80% of least popular items in the system

thereby capturing a filtering algorithms capacity to display a popularity bias.

3.4 Recommendation Algorithms

We test several commonly deployed memory- and model-based CF algorithms, following a similar approach to previous work [69, 62]. Using Surprise [70], a Python library for recommender systems, we formulate our music recommendations as a rating prediction problem where we predict the preference of a target user u for a target artist a . We consider two types of CF algorithms: (1) KNN-based approach: *UserKNNAvg* [71], and (2) factorisation-based approach: *Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF)* [72]. Hyperparameters of *UserKNNAvg* and *NMF* are tuned to give the best performance we can achieve with respect to the rank aware metric, $nDCG$. In addition, we consider two *MostPopular* and *UserItemAvg* algorithms which respectively, recommend the most popular and highest rated artists. We consider these algorithms for a baseline comparison.

A variation of the *leave-l-out* evaluation detailed in [73] is performed whereby we translate the approach to evaluate a *top-n* RS. Drawing influence from the methodology of Said et al. [74] we define 3 parameters: (1) n , the size of the recommendation list generated, (2) N , the number of items selected for each user to appear in the testset. N is constrained to be $> n$ to allow for variance in item recommendations across tested algorithms. (3) M , the minimum number of unique artists listened to by a user. M is constrained to be $> N$ to ensure a non-empty test set is able to be formed for each user. We construct three folds, randomly selecting for each user, N items in their listening history to belong to the fold’s testset and then subsequently removing these listening events from the folds trainset. For each of the algorithms tested, we compute all evaluation metrics and preference ratios over each fold and then subsequently report average performance. In our work we set $N = 10$, $M = 20$ and $n = 5$, thereby generating top-5 recommendation lists. We consider a user’s testset of size N as the sample space for recommendations to be formed. We highlight that this methodology can produce unconventionally high $nDCG@n$ results due to underlying dependencies on the N and n constraints imposed. We therefore

emphasise that whilst the evaluation results attained are comparable in the context of this work, caution is advised when drawing comparisons to external top-n RS literature as recommendation lists will likely be formed and evaluated differently.

3.5 Experimental Design

We set up three experimental designs to evaluate variations in gender BD across recommended artists and user groups for the two datasets. Experiment 1 is a real-world scenario in which male and female gender distributions are representative of those in both datasets. Experiment 2 is an extreme scenario in which all users have high levels of preference ratio, representing extreme listening preferences towards artists of a specific gender. Experiment 3 is a simulated scenario in which all users have balanced preference ratios. We consider users whose maximum PR lies within the range of 0.5 ± 0.05 as our sample space.

Experiment 1. We generate recommendations for a sample of all users for which gender can be identified. In the LFM-1b dataset, we limit the size of this sample to be 30% randomly chosen of all male and female users in the whole dataset (approx 12,000 users), due to computational constraints. The size of the user sample for the LFM-360k dataset was also constrained to be approximately the same size as samples for the LFM-1b dataset. User and artist gender distributions in both samples are representative of overall gender distributions in the entirety of both datasets. We therefore use this experiment to consider the case of gender bias propagation under a real world scenario, assessing the extent to which BD with respect to gender may differ across datasets.

Experiment 2. We generate recommendations only for a sample of male and female users which have high preference ratios in the dataset, thereby simulating an extreme scenario under which all users are highly biased towards one artist gender group in their listening preferences. For the LFM-1b dataset, we select the top 30% of both male and female user groups with the highest maximum input preference ratios, maintaining both the proportions of male and female users in the datasets,

Figure 3: Input Preference Ratio (PR) distributions: LFM-1b (*top*) and LFM-360k (*bottom*).

and the sample size of experiment 1. For the LFM-360k dataset, we sample users from both male and female user groups maintaining the distribution of male and female users in the original dataset. The final user sample has approximately the same sample size as that of the LFM-1b user sample.

Figure 3 shows the distributions of users' input preference ratio towards male and female artist groups. For both datasets considered in this study, it shows that only around 20% of users have a preference ratio towards male artists lower than 0.8. On the contrary, 80% of users have a preference ratio lower than 0.2 towards female artists. Due to the disproportionate amount of users with extreme preferences for male artists across both datasets, a random sampling methodology proposed does little to assess extreme preference towards female artists, resulting in a situation very similar to experiment 1. To resolve this, we further limit our sample space to only users who have extreme preference for female artists, with input preference

ratio towards female artists > 0.6 . This results in a sample size reduction to 100 users for the LFM-1b dataset, and 800 users for the LFM-360k dataset. Although reduced in size in comparison to experiments 1, we believe such experimental designs to be fundamental to measure the extent to which the treatment of users with extreme preferences differs across artist genders. Experiment 2 represents a situation opposite to the one proposed in experiment 1, thanks to which we can assess if bias propagation is not embedded in the gender *per se*, but is a result of pre-existing bias.

Experiment 3. We generate recommendations only for a sample of male and female users which have preference ratios of 0.5 ± 0.05 , thereby simulating an extreme scenario under which all users have minimal input preference towards one artist gender. This experiment is used as a test case to consider if preference distortions are a product of extreme input preferences towards one artist gender (present in experiments 1 and 2) or are dependent on other dimensions of *user-item* configurations. Sample sizes for both datasets are constrained to the maximum which we can attain. As visualised in Figure 3, sample sizes for both datasets are significantly smaller than for experiment 1 as result of the vast majority users having highly polarised listening preferences. For LFM-360k we are able to obtain a larger user sample (approximately 1000) in comparison to LFM-1b (approximately 200) as a product of larger sample space, a product of the greater number of users in the dataset. Proportions of user genders are observed to be comparable to global distributions for both datasets as displayed in Table 2 suggesting the capacity to have a non-bias gender preference is not solely reserved for male or female users. For both dataset samples we observe a rise by approximately 20% in the proportion of female artists (and corresponding reduction for male artists) with respect to global gender distribution levels shown in Table 2.

Chapter 4

Results

In this chapter, we report the results of our three preliminary offline experiments. *BD* and *PR* plots are included for each of the experiments detailed alongside accuracy and beyond accuracy metric results for experiment 1 with the LFM-1b dataset. We report all other accuracy and beyond accuracy results attained in the appendix of this document due to page constraints. In section 4.4 we present a discussion of our findings, reasoning about the potential causes and implications of variations in disparity across the three experimental designs.

4.1 Experiment 1 - Whole Population

We report in Figure 4 *PR*, and in Figure 5 *BD* results obtained with the LFM-1b dataset. Figure 6 and Figure 7 *PR* and *BD* results respectively for the LFM-360K dataset. The dotted lines in Figure 4 and Figure 6 represent input *PR* whereas the plot's bars display output *PR* computed from generated recommendation lists. With regard to pre-existing bias, users in both datasets display high and low input *PR* for male and female artists respectively, thereby in line with the findings of Millar [18]. In addition, for both artist genders input *PR* can be seen to be higher by users who share the same gender as the artist. With regard to bias propagation after recommendation, all recommendation models tested result in a positive *BD* for male artists for which there is minimal variance in treatment across user genders.

Figure 4: Preference Ratio (PR) results for LFM-1b dataset for experiment 1 (*top left*), and experiment 2 (*top right*) and experiment 3 (*bottom left*).

The popularity-based algorithm results in the highest levels of BD for both male and female users, whilst the NMF and $UserKNNAvg$ algorithms tested result in the lowest absolute levels of BD with marginal difference in bias propagation across the two algorithms. Furthermore, our findings show male users to be more affected by bias propagation in the LFM-1b dataset whilst for LFM-360K, we observe bias propagation to be greater for female users thereby inline with the findings of Lin et al. [62]. With regard to BD for female artists, negative levels are observed for all algorithms tested. The *MostPopular* algorithm results in the lowest levels of BD due to female artists having significantly lower popularity for both datasets tested,

Figure 5: Bias Disparity (BD) results for LFM-1b dataset for experiment 1 (*top left*), experiment 2 (*top right*) and experiment 3 (*bottom left*).

as shown in Table 2. We observe bias propagation to be greater for recommendations generated using the LFM-1b dataset reflected in the lower *long-tail percentage* attained. This suggests that users in the LFM-1b dataset may be more subject to a popularity bias in comparison to LFM-360k which may translate to increased levels of gender *BD* due to female artists proportionally residing less in the top-head. Together, our findings suggest that differences in bias propagation across the two datasets may be traced to pre-existing bias entering the system in the form of listening events.

4.2 Experiment 2 - Extreme Preferences

Considering users with extreme preferences for female artists we observe the inverse scenario of experiment 1, such that BD is positive for female artists and negative towards male artists, as shown in Figure 4. For both datasets, we comment that one cause of such disparity is a dramatic imbalance in users’ listening preferences, which then subsequently propagates through to other users’ recommendations. Our findings show that such bias propagation is not reserved for male artists on the platform and can, under extreme scenarios emerge in the opposite manner. For both memory- and model-based approaches tested we observe significant differences in BD : NMF results in the smallest absolute BD increase thereby reflecting a user’s input preference, whereas the neighbour-based $UserKNN_{Avg}$ increases absolute BD levels towards whichever user-artist preference is in the majority. The tendency of NMF to propagate less bias, positively or negatively speaking, in comparison to the other models is also reflected in the results obtained from the beyond-accuracy metrics evaluation. Indeed, for experiment 2 NMF achieves the high levels of coverage, recommending wider subsets of artists, and at the same time high levels of recommendation spread. Together these results suggest that the model-based algorithm considered in this study is capable of achieving a higher level of diversification in the outcomes in comparison to the memory-based model. Translated to our scenario, it means that NMF is the algorithm that focuses less on recommending a specific gender group, avoiding the exacerbation of pre-existing bias in the dataset that other

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.010	0.595	0.676	*0.734
nDCG	0.012	0.663	0.793	*0.880
coverage	1.7E-04	0.364	*0.558	0.552
spread	2.322	11.85	*12.84	12.72
longtail %	0	0.027	0.053	*0.054

Table 4: Experiment 1 evaluation results on the LFM-1b dataset. Values in bold represent the top value, while marked with * are results where the difference is statistically significant, according to a t-test with $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure 6: Preference Ratio (PR) results for LFM-360k dataset for experiment 1 (*top left*), experiment 2 (*top right*) and experiment 3 (*bottom left*).

recommendation algorithms exhibit. Again, the effect of bias propagation is seen to be more amplified in the case of the LFM-1b dataset.

4.3 Experiment 3 - Balanced Preferences

Considering users with balanced listening preferences we observe a negative BD towards male artists after recommendation generation and positive towards females across both datasets. This implies that in a scenario where users are diverse in their preference, this may still not be reflected in music recommendations whereby one

Figure 7: Bias Disparity (BD) results for LFM-360k dataset for experiment 1 (*top left*), and experiment 2 (*top right*) and experiment 3 (*bottom left*).

artist group is still under-represented. Whilst extreme preference for one gender can direct filtering algorithms to induce disparity which favours a prevalent gender preference amongst users, the following experimental scenario demonstrates how, even with minimal *pre-existing bias* entering the system, algorithmic recommendation can still at an OSA level, distort user preference inducing BD . With regard to differences in bias propagation across filtering algorithms, *NMF* once again results in the smallest absolute BD levels meanwhile *MostPopular* produces the greatest levels of absolute BD . The distribution of BD for the *MostPopular* algorithm is similar to the results obtained in experiment 2 with extreme preference for female

artists. Furthermore, we observe a rise in the proportion of long tail recommendations in comparison to experiment 1 for both datasets suggesting that not only are female artists most popular among users with balanced listening preferences, but also, that they are less likely to have popularity at a global level such that they are less probable to exist in the top-head. Again, we also observe users in LFM-1b to be significantly more affected by a gender bias propagation reflected in the drastic drop in coverage as previously highlighted in experiment 1.

4.4 Discussion

In our work we show both memory- and model-based CF approaches tested display a tendency to propagate bias towards the artist group most preferred by the collective user group (*NMF* to a lesser degree). Despite this finding, it is crucial to highlight that the cause of such treatment may be fundamentally different depending on the filtering methodology deployed and thus, the means in which one may seek to resolve such issues is highly context dependent. For instance, nearest neighbour based approaches may be more subject to a *popularity bias* whereby unfair treatment is propagated indirectly. For model-based approaches such as *NMF* tested in our work, it is possible that a sensitive attribute such as gender (or an amalgamation of this) may be derived in the latent space [3] and thus, gender can be discriminated against directly. Although beyond the scope of this work, such differentiations are highlighted to contextualise the potential practical applications of this work.

Ultimately, the findings of this work sheds light on the significance of *user-item* configurations and *pre-existing bias* acting as input for an mRS. Our work evidences *BD* to be both amplified and directed in extreme scenarios under which all users have extreme preference. Furthermore, we show such applications not to be exclusively reserved for male artists. In an “upside down” world we show bias can conversely propagate towards female artists. Perhaps most interestingly, our findings show that, even in a balanced scenario whereby all users have a relatively unbiased artist gender preference and hence there is minimal *pre-existing bias* entering the system in this sense, *BD* is still evidenced to arise. This suggests that whilst input preference

can determine the directionality of bias propagation, additional dimensions of *user-item* configurations or furthermore, hyper-parameter configurations may also play a role in determining degree and direction. Such observations are suggested as topics of future work, detailed further in section 5.2.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Conclusion

Studies of gender bias in music preferences, conducted in fields such as Music Psychology and Gender Studies, have already evidenced how socio-cultural factors are responsible for disparate treatment of non-male artists. Likewise, mainstream media has highlighted the disproportionate gender representation in the popular music industry leading to growing concerns of a patriarchal hierarchy still being present to this day. With the socio-technical perspective now being commonly applied to the field of MIR, the potential for such disproportionate values to be embedded through human arrangement, social practices, and technical artefacts is an accepted phenomena. Notwithstanding, relatively little research has been conducted in the field of MIR exploring the role of existing technology in mitigating or amplifying a gender bias - a void which this research aims to fill.

In line with the studies on *bias disparity* in mRS literature, we show how recommendation outcomes can actually impact a gender bias offline in generated top-n recommendation lists. Using a binary gender classification, where users and artists are classified as male and female, we have shown how at different levels, recommender systems can play a role in propagating a *pre-existing bias*. In addition, simulating an “upside down” world where people have a much higher preference towards fe-

male artists, we still find evidence of an exacerbation of that bias. Our results show that gender bias can be propagated by CF-based recommendations, according to the bias present in the data. Phrased differently, *user-item* configuration and the *pre-existing biases* they embody have the potential to control the directionality of CF recommendation at a global user level.

Furthermore, our work finds evidence that CF can also induce new forms of bias not present in the data. In this instance, *BD* is found to occur towards female artists. These findings suggest that whilst *pre-existing* bias in the form of listening histories can determine the direction of a bias propagation, other underlying biases (such as *technical* and *situational bias*) may be embedded in other dimensions of *user-item* configurations which in turn, guide music recommendation leading to the exhibiting of a gender bias.

Together, our findings suggests that *BD* is not exclusively driven by user listening preference, but rather guided by it. Underlying CF parameter configurations (e.g. latent factor configuration, number of neighbours) and *user-item* configurations (e.g. matrix dimensions and sparsity) may also have a great influence in the induction of such disparity. Although out of the scope of this work, we suggest the latter as future works to extend this research further as detailed in Section 5.2 of this document.

5.2 Future Work

The limitations of this research are several due to computational constraints, data sparsity and project restrictions. In particular, we outline 3 main limitations which we suggest as topics for future works to build upon.

- **Binary classification of gender:** is an oversimplification of gender representation. The state of the art perspective of gender from both natural and social science domains is often non-binary, where male and female are just one of the many genders by which an individual may choose to identify. Binary definitions of gender have been widely critiqued to be socially constructed through

routine gendered performances [19, 17], thereby considering gender to be only binary in this work is both limiting and to some degree, reinforcing of such binary logic. We suggest future works to explore how such conclusions drawn in this work may translate to music recommendation on sample of non-binary artists. A significant contribution of future works would be to further develop a gender assignment system for artists in both Last.fm datasets which is not solely reliant on MusicBrainz meta-data which, as we argue in Section 2.1.2, offers a limited, sparse representation of non-binary gender. We suggest for future works to study the temporal effects of an mRS in propagating a gender bias. Indeed, this could be achieved at an OSA level experimentally, through the iterative generation of item recommendations, modelling user consumption behaviour to study the temporal effects of mRS in distorting *gender bias*. Furthermore, this effect could also be measured as a user-centric effect. One means in which this question could be approached would be to consider the effect of algorithmic influence on a user’s music consumption over time. As raised in the works of Anderson et al. [49], to what degree does one’s preference in the music domain tend towards *organic* vs *algorithmic* influence over time?

- **CF parameter configuration experiments:** Our work does not empirically explore the role of mRS parameter configurations in inducing a *BD*. Although the role of such configurations has been experimentally considered directly with respect to *BD* in RS literature [9], the role of such model configurations propagating gender bias in a real life scenario is yet to be explored. This substantiates the need for further research exploring the relationships between gender *BD* and CF configurations (e.g. latent factors, k number of neighbours etc.).
- **Relations between n in top- n RS and bias-disparity:** It is evident that smaller n values in top- n RS at a local user level, reduce the potential for proportional representation of artist categories with respect to a user’s listening history. Consider a worse case scenario of generating top- n recommendations

where $n = 1$. In this instance, a recommendation list only has the capacity to reflect 1 item category resulting in binary PR outcomes: $PR_R(G, C) = 1$ or $PR_R(G, C) = 0$. From this example, it is clear that increasing the value of n increases at a local user level, granularity and thereby, the potential for proportional representation. We suggest future works to explore the extent to which local potential for proportional representation translates to a global user scenario - i.e. low BD levels for one user category.

In the works of Camille et al. [75] the potential for diversity of non-personalised recommendations (number of potential neighbouring items) on the audio-visual streaming platform, YouTube, is evidenced to be negatively correlated to diversity of simulated consumption (number of actually accessed items in a simulated random walk). Extending this line of reasoning, we suggest for future works to further explore this relation in the context of personalised top- n mRS, i.e. to what degree does the potential for local diversity (greater n) correlate to the consumption of more diverse content by a user?

Together, we propose a two-fold approach to further continue this line of research: (1) Explore the degree to which potential for local proportional representation of user preference is correlated to global proportional representations of a user category in generated recommendation lists. (2) Model a user's consumption of generated recommendation lists to explore how the local potential for proportional representation correlates to proportional consumption of recommended item categories thereby extending the works of Camille et al. [75].

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Appendix A

First Appendix

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.036	0.698	0.726	*0.835
nDCG	0.043	0.761	0.817	*0.986
coverage	0.006	0.469	0.487	*0.509
spread	2.322	8.370	8.438	*8.533
longtail %	0	0.196	0.232	*0.285

(a) Experiment 2

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.032	0.600	*0.589	0.583
nDCG	0.039	0.649	*0.633	0.616
coverage	0.003	0.450	0.479	*0.499
spread	2.322	9.161	9.295	*9.379
longtail %	0	0.148	0.214	*0.252

(b) Experiment 3

Table 5: Evaluation results on the LFM-1b dataset for experiment 2 (a) and experiment 3 (b). Values in bold represent the top value, while marked with * are results where the difference is statistically significant, according to a t-test with $\alpha = 0.05$.

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.019	0.441	0.446	*0.525
nDCG	0.033	0.894	0.903	*0.980
coverage	2.9E-04	0.499	0.515	*0.647
spread	2.322	11.08	11.41	*11.82
longtail %	0	0.097	0.112	*0.123

(a) Experiment 1

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.046	0.444	0.451	*0.503
nDCG	0.089	0.912	0.925	*0.977
coverage	0.003	0.459	0.475	*0.548
spread	2.322	9.011	9.096	*9.470
longtail %	0	0.253	0.269	*0.313

(b) Experiment 2

	<i>Most Popular</i>	<i>UserItem Avg</i>	<i>UserKNN Avg</i>	<i>NMF</i>
precision	0.028	0.378	0.386	*0.441
nDCG	0.062	0.900	0.911	*0.974
coverage	0.002	0.481	0.482	*0.575
spread	2.322	9.835	9.930	*10.31
longtail %	0	0.260	0.278	*0.319

(c) Experiment 3

Table 6: Evaluation results on the LFM-360k dataset for experiment 1 (a), experiment 2 (b) and experiment 3 (c). Values in bold represent the top value, while marked with * are results where the difference is statistically significant, according to a t-test with $\alpha = 0.05$.

Appendix B

Second Appendix